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University Dental College
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Management of Physical Facilities and Utilization of Operation Theatre at Selected Tertiary Level Hospitals in Dhaka City

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ABSTRACT

An operation theatre complex is the heart of any major surgical hospitals. This cross sectional study was done to identify the physical facilities and assess the utilization of operation theatre in tertiary level hospitals and was conducted in Dhaka Medical College & Hospital and Bangladesh Medical College and Hospital in October 2013. Data were collected through observation checklist, questionnaire, records, registered relevant documents maintained in the operation theatre through cross-sectional survey and analysis were done by using SPSS software program. According to the study 16 general surgery, 14 gynae and 4 other surgeries were performed per month by a surgeon in BMCH, and 11 general surgery, 16 gynae and 5 other surgeries were performed per month by a surgeon in DMCH. More general surgeries were done in BMCH(420) which is less in DMCH (360); but in case of gynae and other surgeries it is less in number in BMCH (90,60) than DMCH (120,360). This study revealed that more general surgeries were done in BMCH compared to DMCH but in case of gynae and other surgeries it was vice versa. Waiting lists should be maintained to ensure patients are treated in order of clinical urgency. The management of waiting period for elective surgery within clinically recommended waiting period should have been a major focus of public and health management attention.

Key words: Operation theatre, sets of equipment for each type of operation, location of post surgical ward, operation room utilization, waiting time of patient, staffing pattern.

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INTRODUCTION:

An operation theatre complex is the heart of any major surgical hospital. An operating theatre, operating room, surgery suite or a surgery centre is a room within a hospital within which surgical and other operations are carried out.¹ Operating theatres were so called in the United Kingdom because they traditionally consisted of semi circular amphitheatres to allow students to observe the medical procedures. The old operating theatre in London is one of the oldest, dating back to 1822.²

The patient is the centre point of a functioning OT complex. Efforts are directed to maintain vital functions, prevent infections or promote healing with safety, comfort and economy.^{3,4}

The establishment and working of the operation theatre needs specialize planning and execution and is not a simple civil engineering work. A 'civil mechanical-electrical-electronic-biomedical' combo effort driven and co-ordinated by the needs, preference and safety of the medical and surgical team forms the basis for starting and maintaining an operation theatre.⁵

In 1921, when University of Dhaka began its journey, the building was handed over to the university administration. At that time, a part of this huge building was used as the university's medical centre, another part as student's dormitory and the rest was the administrative wing of the arts faculty. During the second world war it changed its colour yet again, when it became the American based hospital. At the end of the war the Americans left, but the hospital remained. Through the course of time, the 100 bed hospital of that time is Bangladesh's largest hospital today. After adding 500 beds on October 3, 2013, DMCH is now a 2300 bed hospital. The new beds were added in a new building known as DMCH-2. Medicine department is gradually being shifted to the new building, DMCH-2, which will open with a bone marrow transplantation facility very soon.⁶

Bangladesh Medical College is the first private medical college in Bangladesh. It was established in 1986 by a group of dedicated people called the founder member who were imbued with ideas of providing quality medical education, research and services to people of this country at a reasonable cost. The hospital has an arrangement for 500 inpatients. It is equipped and provides quality health care to the public at a reasonable cost. The entire hospital staffs are dedicated to excellence and service.⁷

Improvement of socio-economic condition causes health awareness among people and in turns effected to increase trend in utilization of hospital services by the people. Expectations of consumers have been increased and they have started questioning the adequacy of patient care not only for quantity of services but also for the quality care provided by the hospital.⁸

Having discussed the above hospital is an essential institution of the community and operation room and theatre is an specialized central area of hospital. The reputation of a hospital depends mostly on outcome of operation theatre department. Thus management of operation theatre in planning, organizing, supervising and controlling the activities of operation theatre is of paramount importance in providing quality hospital services.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design:

It is a descriptive study.

Study Population:

- The study population comprised of all personnel working in OT.
- Records and facilities of Operation Theatre.

Sample Size: Dhaka Medical College and Hospital 20
Bangladesh Medical College and Hospital 20

Study site:

Operation Theatre of Dhaka Medical College & Hospital and Bangladesh Medical College & Hospital.

Sampling Technique: Purposive

Research Tools:

Check list and unstructured questionnaire, SPSS Software

Data Collection:

The physical facilities, organization and operation theatre utilization activities were observed and interview with surgeons and staffs were also done. Data were collected through observation checklist and questionnaire, records, registered relevant

documents maintained in the operation theatre through cross-sectional survey. Data were collected from Dhaka Medical College and Hospital in 7th, 8th, 11th, 13th, 14th, 15th, and 16th October, 2013 and from Bangladesh Medical College and Hospital in 18th, 19th, 20th, 21st, 22nd, and 24th October, 2013.

Data analysis:

Collected data was checked for completeness and clarity. The data was then tabulated and analysed by using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULT

In this study available physical facilities were observed by checklist, interviews with the respondents and their opinion was sought for the organization and management activities.

Table 1: Distribution of the hospitals by utilization of OT in DMCH and BMCH

Variables	Name of Hospitals	
	DMCH	BMCH
Available OT	12	8
Surgeries performed daily	28	15
Canceled surgery per month	20	15
Time schedule	Maintained	Maintained

Table 2: Distribution of the hospitals by monthly surgery performed in DMCH and BMCH

Surgery per month	Name of Hospitals	
	DMCH	BMCH
General Operation	360	420
Gynae operation	120	90
Other operation	360	60

The above table described that everyday in DMCH 360 general, 120 gynae and 360 other operations and in BMCH 420 general, 90 gynae and 60 other operations were done.

Table 3: Distribution of hospitals by surgery performed by each surgeon per Month in DMCH and BMCH

Surgery each surgeon per month	DMCH	BMCH
General Surgery	11	16
Gynae Surgery	16	14
Other Surgery	5	4

It is evident from the above table that 16 general surgery 14 gynae and 4 other surgery were performed per month by a surgeon in BMCH, and 11 general surgery, 16 gynae and 5 other surgeries were performed per month by a surgeon in DMCH.

Table 4: Distribution of OT as per speciality of surgery in DMCH and BMCH

Specialty	Name of Hospitals	
	DMCH	BMCH
General Surgery	5	2
Gyne. and Obs.	1	2
Others	6	4
Total	12	8

The above table described that in DMCH there were 5 general, 1 gyne and 6 other OTs and in BMCH there were 2 general, 2 gyne and 4 other OTs. So the total no of OT were 12 and 8 for DMCH and BMCH respectively.

Table 5: Status of facilities of OT room in DMCH and BMCH

Facilities	Name of the hospitals	
	DMCH	BMCH
OT table with full facilities	12	8
Ventilation	In good functioning condition	In good functioning condition.
Oxygen cylinder	Adequate	Adequate
OT light	Sufficient	Sufficient
CPR Facilities	Available	Available
Equipment Set	Enough	Enough
Central oxygen supply in OT	Yes	Yes

The above table shows that 12 OT tables with full facilities were present in DMCH and 8 in BMCH. Ventilation system was in good functioning condition in both hospitals. Oxygen cylinders were adequate, OT lights were sufficient, CPR facilities were available, equipment sets were enough and central oxygen supply was present in both hospitals under study.

Table 6: Rank order of the opinion of nurses regarding problem they are facing in DMCH and BMCH

DMCH		Rank Order	BMCH	
No. (%)	Problem Facing		Problem Facing	No. (%)
28 (70%)	Shortage of man power	1	Shortage of man power	36 (90%)
12 (30%)	No problem	2	Sluggishness of restriction in entering OT	28 (70%)
8 (20%)	Sluggishness of restriction in entering OT	3	Linen shortage	20 (50%)

The above table shows that most of the respondent in both DMCH {28(70%)} and BMCH {36(90%)} mentioned shortage of manpower as a number 1 problem. 28(70%)of respondents of BMCH mentioned sluggishness of restriction in entering OT as number 2 problem and 12(30%) respondents mentioned they were not facing any problem in OT.

DISCUSSION:

A cross sectional descriptive study was done on management of physical facilities and utilization of operation theatre in tertiary level hospitals, one govt. (DMC) and another was private (BMC). The study was conducted with a view to explore the management status of OT with the help of questionnaire, personal observation and check list. The key elements in the efficient use of operating theatres are: effective management and good communication, trained staff, appropriate facilities, equipment, and operational layout.^{9,10} According to the study 16 general surgery, 14 gynae and 4 other surgeries were performed per month by a surgeon in BMCH, and 11 general surgery, 16 gynae and 5 other surgeries were performed per month by a surgeon in DMCH. Cancellations of surgeries per day were 20 in DMCH and 15 in BMCH and both hospitals maintained their time schedule. More general surgeries were done in BMCH(420) compared to DMCH (360) but in case of gynae and other surgeries it is less in number in BMCH (90,60) than DMCH (120, 360). In this study 12 OT table with full facilities were present in DMCH and 8 in BMCH. For general surgery there were 5 OTs in DMCH and 2 in BMCH. For gynae and obs. 1 OT in DMCH and 2 in BMCH and for other surgeries there were 6 OTs in DMCH and 4 in BMCH. Most of the respondent of BMCH {24(60%)} gave their opinion that increase in manpower can improve the management of OT and most of the respondent of DMCH {10(50%)} gave their opinion that increase in modern equipment can improve the management of OT.

CONCLUSION:

This study revealed that more general surgeries are done in BMCH than DMCH but in case of gynae and other surgeries it is opposite in BMCH than DMCH. There are more general surgeries performed per month by a surgeon in BMCH than DMCH. There are OT tables with full facilities in both DMCH and BMCH. Most of the respondent in both hospitals mentioned shortage of manpower as a number one problem. Per day more surgeries are performed in DMCH than BMCH. There are lacking of modern technology in almost all sectors and standardizations are not followed in many places. It also identifies areas where more improvement effort should be invested.

RECOMMENDATION:

Arrangement of refresher training to enrich knowledge and update skill development for the nursing should be encouraged. Operation lists should be prepared on the day before surgery to enable proper assessment and optimum list arrangement. Standard OT management rule should be followed by the hospital recruitment and retention of trained nursing staff must be enhanced.

The amount and types of surgery performed at each hospital should depend on the demand in the hospital's catchment area, the types of surgery its staff and facilities are credentialed to undertake, and the budget available. Waiting lists should be maintained to ensure patients are treated in order of clinical urgency. The management of waiting period for elective surgery within clinically recommended waiting period should have been a major focus of public and health management attention.

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